

To Weigh or Not to Weigh: Challenges and Solutions for BodyTrace Data

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ABSTRACT

In weight loss studies, examining self-weighing patterns using smart scales is a more reliable measure than self-reporting. Smart scales are broadly available and inexpensive, transmitting the data directly to a study database. This study used BodyTrace™ e-scales to collect individual weights. The aim was to examine whether greater self-weighing frequency is associated with less weight gain after smoking cessation. These data inherently have challenges that require data processing and cleaning before analysis can occur. Weights captured by BodyTrace™ are date/time stamped in Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) and must be converted to the appropriate local time zone to extract the first daily measure. In addition, participants can have multiple daily measurements due to numerous household individuals often using the same scale. We applied two SAS macro programs to update participants' time zone data, correctly identify participants' weight profiles, and used the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) to identify and remove outliers before extracting the first daily measure. In this paper, we explain the challenges, provide snippets of the SAS macro codes that conduct the analytic work related to the preparation of the smart scale data, and briefly discuss the primary analysis and findings of the FIT & QUIT study.

INTRODUCTION

Smart monitoring systems (e.g., e-scales) for clinical research are increasingly widespread (Steinberg et al., 2015; Mao et al., 2017). Collaborative efforts to determine how to store, keep, and access relevant data for research and statistical analysis are necessary to reduce turnaround time and provide immediate action on a real-time basis (Kocak, 2018).

This research proposes two SAS macro programs (%update_timezone and %BodyTraceClean) to update participants' time zone data, correctly identify participants' weight profiles, and use the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) to identify and remove outliers before extracting the first daily measure. The SAS macro program, %BodyTraceClean, augments an existing algorithm SAS macro program, %TPF, to capture the actual profile in a given streaming data from individuals (Kocak, 2018). In our work, we added the use of the GAM to identify and remove outliers from actual profiles prior to analysis and run the process for all participants simultaneously.

We describe the challenges and solutions to working with BodyTrace™ data in Section 2, followed by snippets of the SAS macro programs, %update_timezone and %BodyTraceClean in Section 3. In Section 4, we provide an application of the methods for secondary data analysis for the FIT & QUIT study (Salgado García, 2019). Lastly, we

briefly discuss the primary analysis and findings of the secondary data analysis in Section 5.

SECTION-2: CHALLENGES & SOLUTIONS

To extract the first daily measure of participants, weights captured by BodyTrace™ smart scales must be converted to the appropriate local time for study participants by their time zone and zip code, either in daylight saving time or standard time. Moreover, further data processing is required to discern the actual profiles of study participants in households with multiple members (Table 1).

Table 1: Data Processing Challenges and Solutions for BodyTrace™ data

Challenges	Solutions
1) Weights are date/time stamped in Greenwich time.	SAS macro program %update_timezone updates time zone data from Greenwich Time to the local time zone for study participants based on the parameters given. A snippet of the %update_timezone macro is available in Section 3, Part 1.
2) Discern true profiles of study participants from households with multiple members.	SAS macro program %BodyTraceClean uses a dual combination approach to perform data cleaning operations to identify the actual profile of participants in studies using BodyTrace™ scales (1) Augmentation to the %TPF SAS macro program (Kocak, 2018), and (2) application of the generalized additive model (GAM) (Ross et al., 2018) to identify and remove outliers from actual profiles prior to analysis. Section 3, Part 2, contains a snippet of the %BodyTraceClean macro program.

SECTION-3: SAS ALGORITHM SNIPPETS

The SAS macro program %update_timezone performs data processing operations to convert the Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) timezone collected by BodyTrace™ e-scales to local time zones for study participants. A description of the parameters necessary for the %update_timezone macro program is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. %update_timezone SAS macro parameter description.

INPUT_DATA: Original dataset. Data should have at least 5 columns in long format: ID, date, time, weight, addresszip.
INTERIM_DATA: Dataset where transformations will take place to ensure integrity of original data files.
OUTPUT_DATA: Output dataset with time zones modified.

Part 1: Snippet of %update_timezone SAS Macro Program:

```
/* Macro to update Time Zone from Greenwich Time to Local Time Zone */
```

```

%macro update_timezone(input_data=, interim_data=, output_data=);

/*-----Additional Data Processing Code-----*/
/* -----Refer to GitHub Repository for Complete Syntax-----*/
/*-----(https://github.com/ningsun19/BodyTrace.git)-----*/

/*Note:*/
/* (1) studyid = 2484 (Arizona ZIP Code: 85138, MST ONLY) */
/* (2) studyid = 517 doesn't have ZIP Code nor timezone - updated to Central
Time*/

/* Change All GMT to Local Time */
proc sql;
/* Eliminating the redundancy here */
alter table &interim_data
add GMT num label = 'GMT' format = datetime20.
add Local_datetime num label = 'Local_datetime' format = datetime20.
add Local_timezone char label='Local_timezone'
add Local_Date num label = 'Local_Date' format = MMDDYY10.
add Local_Time num label='Local_Time' format = TIME20.3
add dst_datebeg_GMT num label = 'dst_datebeg_GMT' format = mmddyy10.
add dst_dateend_GMT num label = 'dst_dateend_GMT' format = mmddyy10.
add dst_time_GMT num label = 'dst_time_GMT' format = TIME20.3
add dst_datetimebeg_GMT num label = 'dst_datetimebeg_GMT' format =
datetime20.
add dst_datetimeend_GMT num label = 'dst_datetimeend_GMT' format =
datetime20.;
update &interim_data
set dst_datebeg_GMT = nwkdom(2, 1, 3, year(date)),
dst_dateend_GMT = nwkdom(1, 1, 11, year(date)),
dst_time_GMT = case
when timezone = 'E' then '06:00:00't
when timezone = 'C' then '07:00:00't
when timezone = 'M' then '08:00:00't
when timezone = 'P' then '09:00:00't
else dst_time_GMT
end;

update &interim_data
set dst_datetimebeg_GMT = dhms(dst_datebeg_GMT, 0, 0, dst_time_GMT),
dst_datetimeend_GMT = dhms(dst_dateend_GMT, 0, 0, dst_time_GMT),
GMT = dhms(date, 0, 0, time);
update &interim_data
set Local_timezone = case
when studyid eq 2484 then "MST"
else
case
when GMT between dst_datetimebeg_GMT and
dst_datetimeend_GMT then
case
when timezone = 'E' then 'EDT'
when timezone = 'C' then 'CDT'
when timezone = 'M' then 'MDT'
when timezone = 'P' then 'PDT'
else Local_timezone
end
else

```

```

                                case
                                when timezone = 'E' then 'EST'
                                when timezone = 'C' then 'CST'
                                when timezone = 'M' then 'MST'
                                when timezone = 'P' then 'PST'
                                _ else Local_timezone
                                end
                                end
                                end;
update &interim_data
set Local_datetime = case
                                when Local_timezone = 'EDT' then
                                    intnx("HOUR", GMT, -4, "SAME")
                                when Local_timezone in ('CDT', 'EST') then
                                    intnx("HOUR", GMT, -5, "SAME")
                                when Local_timezone in ('MDT', 'CST') then
                                    intnx("HOUR", GMT, -6, "SAME")
                                when Local_timezone in ('PDT', 'MST') then
                                    intnx("HOUR", GMT, -7, "SAME")
                                when Local_timezone = 'PST' then
                                    intnx("HOUR", GMT, -8, "SAME")
                                else Local_datetime
                                end;
update &interim_data
set Local_Date = datepart(Local_datetime),
   Local_time = timepart(Local_datetime);

quit;
<more lines>
%mend update_timezone;

```

Part 2: Snippet of %BodyTraceClean SAS Macro Program:

Modified from the %TPF (True Profile Finder) SAS macro program (Kocak, 2018), %BodyTraceClean performs data cleaning operations to identify the actual profile of participants in data captured using BodyTrace™ e-scales. %BodyTraceClean utilizes clinic measurements as 'correct' and applies the generalized additive model methodology to identify and remove outliers from actual profiles (Ross et al., 2018, p. 319). A description of the parameters necessary for the %BodyTraceClean macro is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. %BodyTraceClean SAS macro program parameter description.

DATA: Input dataset. Data should have at least 4 columns in long format: ID, time, weight, data type (i.e., clinical vs. e-scale, see MGROUP below).
PREDBAND: The prediction band around the model prediction beyond which all measurements will be considered not belonging to the correct profile. Default to 8.
WSIZE: Window Size. This is the size of the moving window detecting new 'correct profile' measurements and it starts from the first observation.
TVAR: Time variable
YVAR: Signal variable (e.g., weight)
MGROUP: Measurement Group. This variable identifies a given measurement as 'clinic' or 'data stream' measurement. This is critical to identify as these two

measurement types will be weighed differently in the correct-profile detection process. If you don't have any clinic data, then you still need to create an MGROUP variable and assign the value of 0 to all measurements indicating no clinic measurement.

NOTE: 'Clinical' weight measured at lab have dtype = 1, 'e-scale' measured has dtype = 0.

MTYPE: The code for the 'clinic' measurements in MGROUP variable. Default is 1.

AWEIGHT: The weight of the actual 'clinic' measurements. Default is 10.

MODELCHOICE: The choice of the polynomial model. The variable TT will be created during the operation so you simply specify the model using variable TT.

LOWERBND: The lower bound of measurements below which all measurements are considered not belonging to the correct profile without modeling.

UPPERBND: The upper bound of measurements above which all measurements are considered not belonging to the correct profile without modeling.

TRUEPROFILE: The variable indicating true profile if available. If not, a new code will be added.

OUTNAME: The output dataset name to retain the original data as well as the final profile calls in a variable called FINALPROFILE.

```
*%BodyTraceClean;

%macro BodyTraceClean(data=, predband=8, wsize= 15, tvar=num_days,
yvar=weight, mgroup=dtype, mtype=1,
    aweight=10, modelchoice=tt, lowerbnd=40, upperbnd=200, trueprofile = ,
outname=sampled_data_profile&x);
*tvar: num_days: days since baseline weight was measured
*yvar: weight: participant weights in kg
;

/*-----Additional Data Processing Code-----*/
/* -----Refer to GitHub Repository for Complete Syntax-----*/
/*-----(https://github.com/ningsun19/BodyTrace.git)-----*/

/* GAM model snippet */
title h=2 "ID-%%id&x";
ods exclude all;
proc gam data=&outname;
where finalprofile=1 ;
model weight = loess(&tvar)/method=gcv;
output out=out&x pred resid;
run;
ods exclude none;

data out&x;
set out&x;
outlier_idx = 0;
if r_weight >2.27 or r_weight < -2.27 then outlier_idx = 1;
run;

proc sgplot data=out&x;
scatter x=&tvar y=&yvar / name="points" legendLabel="Weights"
colorresponse=outlier_idx;
```

```

series x=&tvar y=p_&yvar / name="line" legendLabel="Predicted weights"
lineattrs = GRAPHFIT;
discretelegend "points" "line";
run;
<more lines>
%mend BodyTraceClean;

```

SECTION 4: APPLICATION OF METHODS

The %BodyTraceClean macro program discerns the actual profile of participants by assigning a higher weight to clinical data obtained at baseline and 12 months from recruited participants. An example of how the macro program works is presented for ID 121 (Figure 1). Once identified, the generalized additive model (GAM) was applied on the "finalprofile" (i.e., the correct profile of participants) where red circles are outliers, which have absolute residual values larger than 2.27kg (5lb) (Ross et al., 2018, p. 319) (Figure 2) and green diamonds represent the weights from another individual. In cases where participants with similar weights, The SAS %BodyTraceClean macro runs the process for all participants with given parameters. It is essential to check the output plots visually and try different parameters for exceptional cases. For example, participant 2494 displays a household where users of the e-scale had similar weights. Fine-tuning the parameters of the macro code provides an increasingly higher level of detail to discern the actual profile of the study participant (Figures 3 & 4).

Figure 1. SAS %BodyTraceClean macro program discerns the actual profile of study participants (finalprofile = 1). For study participant 121, for example, two additional profiles are identified to have used the BodyTrace™ scale that does not represent the actual study participant (finalprofile 2 & 3).

Figure 2. The Generalized Additive Model (GAM) was applied to identified profiles of study participants, where red circles indicate outliers that have absolute residual values larger than 2.27kg (5lb) (Ross et al., 2018, p. 319).

Figure 3. Application of SAS %BodyTraceClean for participant 2494. A case with household members with similar weights. Modification to the parameters: lowerband (lower value) and predict band (higher value), provides additional detail to discern the actual participant profile (finalprofile = 1).

Figure 4. Application of SAS %BodyTraceClean for participant 2494. A case with household members with similar weights. Modification to the parameters: lowerband (higher value) and predict band (lower value), provides additional detail to discern the actual participant profile (finalprofile = 1).

SECTION 5: FIT & QUIT FINDINGS

This was a secondary data analysis from the FIT & QUIT trial to determine if a greater frequency of self-weighing is associated with less weight gain in the context of smoking cessation. Participants (N = 305) were randomized to one of three 2-month weight interventions (i.e., Stability, Loss, Bibliotherapy), followed by a smoking cessation intervention. Stability and Loss conditions received different types of self-weighing feedback. All participants received BodyTrace™ e-scales at baseline to capture daily self-weighing data over 12 months. The SAS macro programs, %update_timezone and %BodyTraceClean, provided the data cleaning and processing to generate the final data analysis for statistical analysis. General linear models were applied to test the main objective. In short, the self-weighing frequency was (mean ± SD) 2.67 ± 1.84 days/week. The Stability condition had significantly higher self-weighing frequency (3.18 ± 1.72 days/week) compared to the Loss (2.51 ± 1.99 days/week) and the Bibliotherapy conditions (2.22 ± 1.63 days/week). Adjusting for baseline weight and treatment condition, self-weighing 3–4 days/week was associated with weight stability (-0.77 kg, 95% CI: $-2.2946, 0.7474$, $p = 0.3175$), and self-weighing five or more days/week was associated with 2.26 kg weight loss (95% CI: $-3.9249, -0.5953$, $p = 0.008$). A comprehensive description of the FIT & QUIT trial findings is present in Oswald, 2023.

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